

Microstructural corrosion of Mg1Ca1Si alloy in physiological solutions

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Generally, Mg alloys exhibit attractive mechanical properties, therefore they are widely used as structural materials in the automotive and electronics sectors. In recent years, Mg alloys are considered as a new class of biodegradable implant materials. In vitro and in vivo studies have shown that magnesium alloys easily undergo resorption and do not cause allergic reactions. One of disadvantages of magnesium alloys is their low corrosion resistance in physiological solutions. In order to improve the corrosion resistance the modified chitosan coatings were deposited on the surface of Mg1Ca1Si alloy. Fig.1 shows the evolution of OCP and LSV curves obtained for MgCaSi in the Ringer solution. These results have revealed, that the best corrosion resistance exhibit the MgCaSi alloy covered by chitosan layer modified by means of addition of NaF and Na₂SiO₃ salts.

Fig.1. Evolution of OCP (a) and LSV curves obtained for MgCaSi in Ringer solution.

The corrosion mechanism of Mg1Ca1Si magnesium alloys in the Ringer solution was investigated by means of electrochemical techniques like: Linear Sweep Voltammetry (LSV), Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), chronoamperometry were performed. All electrochemical measurements have been performed in the Ringer solution at 37°C and pH = 7.2. The surface analysis after corrosion tests were performed by using FE-SEM. Moreover, the chemical analysis of the solution after corrosion tests were investigated by ICP-MS and UV-vis spectroscopy.

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